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PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL AND STRESS CONDITIONS IN WOMEN AT THREATENED PREMATURE BIRTH

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ANNOTATION

The purpose of this original research work was to identify stress factors and psychopathological conditions in women at risk of preterm birth. The study involved 168 women at risk for preterm birth. At the time of the study, all women were undergoing drug therapy to prolong pregnancy. The study identified the determinants of the negative psycho-emotional state of women at risk of premature birth. The presence of a negative psycho-emotional state and maladaptive states significantly complicates the course of pregnancy. To increase fertility rates and reduce the risk of premature birth, a comprehensive intervention of medical and psychological measures is needed to prolong pregnancy, stabilize the psycho-emotional state of the mother and prevent pregnancy complications.

Keywords: premature birth, depression, stress, anxiety.

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ПСИХОПАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И СТРЕССОВЫЕ СОСТОЯНИЯ У ЖЕНЩИН ПРИ УГРОЗЕ ПРЕЖДЕВРЕМЕННЫХ РОДОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью этой оригинальной исследовательской работы было выявление стрессовых факторов и психопатологических состояний у женщин с риском преждевременных родов. В исследовании приняли участие 168 женщин из группы риска преждевременных родов. На момент исследования все женщины проходили медикаментозную терапию для продления беременности. В результате исследования выявлены детерминанты негативного психоэмоционального состояния женщин из группы риска преждевременных родов. Наличие негативного психоэмоционального состояния и дезадаптивных состояний существенно осложняет течение беременности. Для повышения рождаемости и снижения риска преждевременных родов необходимо комплексное вмешательство медицинских и

психологических мероприятий, направленных на пролонгирование беременности, стабилизацию психоэмоционального состояния матери и предупреждение осложнений беременности.

Ключевые слова: преждевременные роды, депрессия, стресс, тревога.

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MUDDATDAN OLDIN TUG'ILISH XAVFI BOR AYOLLARNING PSIXOPATOLOGIK VA STRESS HOLATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu asl tadqiqot ishining maqsadi erta tug'ilish xavfi bo'lgan ayollarda stress omillari va psixopatologik sharoitlarni aniqlash edi. Tadqiqotda erta tug'ilish xavfi ostida bo'lgan 168 ayol ishtirok etdi. Tadqiqot vaqtida barcha ayollar homiladorlikni uzaytirish uchun dori terapiyasini o'tkazdilar. Tadqiqotda erta tug'ilish xavfi ostida bo'lgan ayollarning salbiy psixo-emotsional holatini belgilovchi omillar aniqlandi. Salbiy psixo-emotsional holat va noto'g'ri holatlarning mavjudligi homiladorlik jarayonini sezilarli darajada murakkablashtiradi. Tug'ilish darajasini oshirish va erta tug'ilish xavfini kamaytirish uchun homiladorlikni uzaytirish, onaning psixo-emotsional holatini barqarorlashtirish va homiladorlikning asoratlarini oldini olish bo'yicha tibbiy va psixologik chora-tadbirlarning kompleks aralashuvi zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: erta tug'ilish, depressiya, stress, tashvish.

Introduction

The special location of the Kaliningrad region and unfavorable environmental conditions entail certain socio-economic and medical-social problems. Poor physical health of the population affects reproductive health, in particular, the reproductive health of women. Medical-biological, psychosocial and behavioral factors together play a decisive role in determining the course and outcome of pregnancy.

According to WHO, every sixth woman's pregnancy is interrupted by spontaneous miscarriage or preterm birth (PL) [8,10]. In the Kaliningrad region over the past three years there has been no tendency to improve these indicators (Table 1).

Table 1

Indicators of premature births in the Kaliningrad region

Indicators	2015	2016	2017
PB at less than 36 completed weeks of pregnancy	10.39 %	10.67 %	9.35%
Pregnancy at less than 32 completed weeks of pregnancy	3.04%	2.68%	1.54%
Pregnancy at less than 28 completed weeks of pregnancy	1.07%	0.95%	0.51%
Disability percentage of premature babies	56.7%	59.4%	55.9%
Early neonatal mortality	6.44%	7.71%	7.54%

The main causes of premature birth include the following:

- infectious and inflammatory processes;
- disturbances in the functioning of the hypothalamic-pituitary axis due to stress;
- bleeding;
- overstretching of the uterus [6, 7, 9].

Previous studies have shown a relationship between the frequency of pregnancy complications and the presence of psycho-emotional disorders [2, 3, 4, 5]. Severe stress disorders and negative events, in particular the threat of miscarriage, can lead to various psychopathological disorders [1,5].

The purpose of this article is to consider and identify factors in the negative psycho-emotional state of women with threatened premature birth.

Materials and methods

The study took place on the basis of the State Autonomous Institution KO "ROC" in Kaliningrad. The study involved 168 women at risk for threatened preterm birth. At the time of the study, all women were undergoing drug therapy to prolong pregnancy. The average age of the women examined was 28 years (± 4.5). In 35.7% of women with threatened pregnancy, it was the first pregnancy, in 14.3% it was the second, and the remaining 50% of women had a history of three or more pregnancies.

Analysis of anamnestic data showed that 46.4% of women had more than one perinatally significant infection. The presence of extragenital pathology (diseases of the cardiovascular system, liver and gastrointestinal tract), chronic inflammation of the uterine appendages, and uterine fibroids significantly increase the risk of developing threatening premature birth ($p < 0.05$). According to microbiological and morphological studies of placentas, 40% of threatened premature births are caused by intrauterine infection.

To determine the level of mental health, the following were used: a clinical interview, a clinical questionnaire for identifying and assessing neurotic conditions (K.K. Yakhin, D.M. Mendelevich), clinical scales and psychological methods: "Hamilton Anxiety Scale" and "Rose of Quality of Life" according to I. A. Gundarov.

Statistical data processing was carried out using the following criteria: chi-square; F – Fischer criterion.

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the Committee on Human Experimentation; the requirements of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki and its 1996 revision; requirements of the Resolution of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States of November 18, 2005 No. 26–10 "On the Model Law "On the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity in Biomedical Research in the CIS Member States." All women gave written consent to participate in the study and to publish the results.

Results

The clinical interview was aimed at studying the factors that provoke the negative psycho-emotional state of pregnant women with threatening birth defects. Data from a clinical interview made it possible to identify categories that most fully reflect the direction of women's experiences:

- problems of somatic and reproductive health;
- features of experiencing threatening PD;
- personal characteristics of a woman;
- experiencing an authoritarian and emotionally cold attitude on the part of significant loved ones (relationships with the husband, with the parental family).

Analysis of the level of anxiety (Me [Q1-Q3]) and quality of life indicators revealed high values of somatic (4.0 [0.5-6.0]; $p < 0.001$), mental (4.0 [2.5-6.0]; $p < 0.001$), neurovegetative (2.0 [1.0-4.0]; $p < 0.001$), total anxiety (12.0 [5.0-12.5]; $p < 0.001$). A statistically significant relationship was identified between an increase in the level of anxiety and a decrease in quality of life (Table 2).

Table 2

Relationship between increased anxiety levels and decreased quality of life

Group of pregnant women	Hamilton anxiety scale	Quality of life assessment ("Quality of Life Rose")		Total
		≤ 46 points	≥ 46 points	
n=168	≥ 14 points	51(80.9%)	12 (19.04%)	63 (37.5%)

	≤ 14 points	21(20%)	84 (80%)	105 (62.5%)
	Total:	72 (100%)	96 (100%)	168 (100%)
$\chi^2=26.20; p<0.001$				

The results obtained using the survey for identifying and assessing neurotic conditions (K.K. Yakhin, D.M. Mendelevich) showed that the majority of women have neurotic manifestations - scores exceeding 1.28 indicate a healthy state, while as scores less than -1.28 indicate a severe painful condition. The most pronounced indicators were on the anxiety scale (Table 3).

Table 3

Analysis of mental state indicators using a questionnaire for identifying and assessing neurotic conditions

Method scales	Average value	Standard deviation	P – level
Anxiety scale	-3.52	±2.24	0.001
Neurotic Depression Scale	-0.75	±2.12	0.001
Asthenia scale	2.03	±1.56	0.01
Hysterical Response Scale	5.87	±1.09	0.05
Obsessive-phobic disorder scale	6.35	±1.02	0.05
Autonomic Disorders Scale	-0.64	±1.78	0.01

Discussion

The results of the analysis of the somatic health of women with threatening birth defects indicate that most of them have problems associated with reproductive (46.4%) and somatic health (35%). The most common causes of threatening birth defects are infectious diseases, in particular intrauterine infections (40%).

An analysis of the system of relations in the parental family shows that most women report negative relationships. The prevailing statements are “cold” (49.3%), “unemotional” (39%), “authoritarian” (29.9%), and “offense” (44%). Many women associate the main negative characteristics with their relationship with their mother - they perceive her as “not understanding” (35.2%), “distant” (43%), “not taking part in their life” (46%).

Relationships with their husbands are considered by the majority of women (58%) in the context of various difficulties: many note the lack of emotional support (61%), coldness (57%). Many women pointed to the instability of relationships (46%), indifference on the part of their husbands (57%), and loneliness (46%).

A significant indicator was also the factor of a woman’s attitude towards herself and her pregnancy. Many noted fear for their health and the health of their child (76%), negative emotional experiences (68%), and lack of self-confidence (35%).

All these factors individually and collectively provoke a decrease in the quality of life, which in turn leads to an increase in the level of anxiety.

As a result of the analysis of the “Clinical Questionnaire for the Identification and Assessment of Neurotic Conditions,” the following characteristics characteristic of women with threatened preterm birth were noted: increased anxiety (68%), emotional instability (65%), emotional excitability (47%), internal restlessness (65%), increased sensitivity to negative events (67%), symptoms of low mood (37%) are noted - this is evidenced by data on scales of anxiety, neurotic depression and autonomic disorders.

Weakened somatic health, the presence of infections and diseases that potentially threaten the life and health of the child entail an unstable psycho-emotional state of women, manifested in an increase in the level of anxiety and the formation of depressive components. Negative relationships in the family, both in the parental and in the relationship with the husband, are an additional source of stress, which contributes to the development of emotional instability and can provoke neurotic manifestations. The highest rates of increased anxiety were observed in women with a negative mental state, with problems in relationships with loved ones, and with infectious diseases.

Conclusion

The characteristics and dynamics of the psycho-emotional states of women with threatening PD are associated with the following factors, which can act both in isolation and in combination:

- problems of somatic and reproductive health;
- features of experiencing threatening PD;
- personal characteristics of a woman;
- experiencing an authoritarian and emotionally cold attitude on the part of significant loved ones.

The study identified the following determinants of the negative psycho-emotional state of women with threatened preterm birth:

- reduced level of quality of life;
- increased rates of somatic, mental, neurovegetative anxiety, which may indicate a high probability of developing a neurotic state;
- the formation of an alarming variant of the psychological component of the gestational dominant is observed;
- increased emotional excitability, indicating the pregnant woman's concern for her health and for the health of her child.

The presence of a negative psycho-emotional state and maladaptive states significantly complicates the course of pregnancy. To improve fertility rates and reduce the risk of premature birth, a comprehensive intervention of medical and psychological measures aimed at prolonging pregnancy, stabilizing the psycho-emotional state of the mother and preventing pregnancy complications is necessary.

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1 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

АННАЛЫ КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ ДИСЦИПЛИН

ТОМ 1, НОМЕР 2

КЛИНИК ФАНЛАР ЙИЛНОМАСИ

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2

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